

CHARACTER CREATION SKILLS OF LUKMON BORIKHAN

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Abstract. The article examines the skill of character creation in Lukmon Borikhan's short story "Sirli muallim" ("Mysterious Teacher").

Keywords. story, image, character, artistic idea, work of Lukmon Borikhan, artistic skill.

One of the writers contributing to the enrichment of Uzbek prose with works on various topics and characters of a unique nature is Lukmon Borikhan. The author, who first entered the field of literature with the story "Begimkul Katta", over the years has written "The man who see Khizr", "Mysterious teacher", "A woman does not believe in tears", "The girl in search", "The sun has not yet set", " He brought his stories to the readers' attention, such as "A drop of youth". The characters created in the stories of the writer showed their approach to social relations, their national identity, and their inner world.

Character creation requires a lot of skill from every creator. Character vividly expresses the characteristics of people belonging to a certain period, environment, profession, age, gender. In the images created by the artist, he expresses his individual views, his attitude to spiritual and moral issues. The character reflects the writer's approach to society representatives and social relations, his aesthetic assessment of life events.

Lukman Borikhan's short story "Mysterious Teacher" is devoted to an interesting and topical issue. In the short story, the author covered the life of teachers, their activities and interactions in the educational institution. At the same time, the work attracts attention with its unconventional method of expression. The

composition of the work was made on the basis of the narrator's visit to the 41st settlement with a special assignment to study the incident, and his acquaintance with the folder containing the explanatory letters of the school staff from among the investigative documents. So, the main reality of the work is explained in the explanatory letters of such characters as school director K. Kolkanov, Ulash agronomist-poet, school scientific director Norkhol Khushbokova, school deputy director B.B. Boymurodov, teacher H. Khurramovich, elementary school teacher Eshbolta given As a result, the unique character of these characters, the spiritual world, their psyche is deeply revealed. Each of the heroes of the story writes an explanatory letter to justify himself, and also gives information about his personal dignity. Each character is manifested by its own nature and human experiences, personal attitude to events. As a result, the life of the society depicted by the writer is shown in its entirety. In the reality centered around Najot Ghaibulla, various problems of the society appeared. Lack of attention to the field of education; insufficient supply of school supplies due to economic shortages; low attitude towards the teaching profession in the society; that the financial condition of the representatives of the educational sector is not satisfactory; It can be seen that economic as well as spiritual changes in society have a negative effect on the psyche of people of knowledge and enlightenment, and these aspects can be seen in the opinions of the heroes of the work, who reacted to the events, and in the story based on these opinions. It is also reflected in his past.

Most of the heroes of the story are people who love and are devoted to their profession according to the writer's artistic goal. They are embodied as people who are fond of children and books, devoted to their profession. In addition, their human qualities include patience, perseverance, sincerity, and understanding of the pain of others. Quoted from the language of Najot Ghaybulla: "The person who opens a new world in the innocent hearts of children, who puts the magic of knowledge in their hearts is a teacher" [1.128], "A teacher's life is full of courage and selflessness !" [1.128], the opinions were expressed about the knowledgeable and devoted people

of the field of education. But there are also those who try to complicate the lives of people working in such a complicated environment. Domla H. Khurramovich and Ulash agronomist-poet belong to this category of people. They are embodied in the work as an artistic representation of people who try to find dirt under their fingernails, who use other people's shortcomings or mistakes for their own personal gain, who always try to be an obstacle in the path of selfless or talented people.

In fact, Najot Ghaibulla, the main character, is in the center of the events. This character is the hero who created the knot of the work and acquired a special character. His artistic world is revealed through the eyes of others, the attitude of those around him.

The name of the hero of the story was also chosen according to his essence in the work. He supposedly brought salvation to the field of education. In addition, he was a savior who disappeared for the school in the reader's imagination, like the heroes of the work.

On the one hand, thoughts about Najot Ghaybulla indicate that he is a mysterious person, and on the other hand, whoever he is, they arouse positive feelings in the reader. Najot Ghaibulla is the image of a teacher in the writer's imagination and ideal. According to the creator's ideological goal of the work, it is economical from the point of view, exemplary in terms of behavior and appearance, and has an enviable level of knowledge. Most importantly, he is a dedicated person. He loves children and school. He wants to create good conditions for students, to organize high-quality lessons and tries to do so, and enjoys his work. What he does for the children, his enthusiasm is selfless, he does not seek interests such as making a positive impression on the supervisors or pleasing someone. This teacher, who teaches geography, makes children so interested in the lesson that even Norkhol Khushbakova, who joined her training as an inspector, feels like they are walking along the beach with her, breathing in the air of that place.

Some of the teachers who work with Najot Ghaibulla hate him: the reason for this was the children's attitude towards him, rushing to his classes. In the opinion of

his colleagues, he "distributed medicine" to make children lose their way and obey him. There are many people who admire him on the one hand and envy him on the other hand. After he started working at the school , the atmosphere in the school also changes, that is, some will imitate him and make a change in their behavior, and some will look for evil in this situation. In this way, the writer describes the state of society, the complex aspects of relationships between people, people's discusses problems in the spiritual world.

"If I'm lucky, I'll be back," he said, stopping at the threshold, and a broken smile spread across his face and eyes. - I will correct my documents and return to your ranks. Wait for me, my dear brothers!" [1.128]. Najot Ghaybulla's attitude towards the teaching profession, his true sense of responsibility for children's education and his sincere attitude towards his students, and the writer aims to increase the reader's hope that he will return to his beloved school. Through this, in our opinion, the artist's confidence is expressed that in the future the rise and development of the field of education, the centers of education and training will have dedicated people who are truly worthy of their profession.

In conclusion, it can be said that the characters created in Lukmon Borikhon's story "Mysterious Teacher" have their own views on social relations in the society, and during the events that took place, they show positive or negative aspects of the spiritual world. and at the same time, they stand out as characters who have shown their height in these processes with their inner experiences. The writer's unique skillful approach to the image of the characters is one of the important factors that served to increase the artistic value of the story.

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